

Erythrose revealed as furanose forms

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5 **A non-conventional vaporization method, using laser ablation of solid NaCl doped with D-erythrose, has been used to bring this sugar into the gas phase for rotational study. The jet cooled rotational spectrum of this C₄ monosaccharide reveals the existence of two furanose forms, one α envelope and one β twist. Cooperative hydrogen bond networks and anomeric effect have been found to be the main stabilization factors of the detected structures.**

The growing importance of oligosaccharide structure in biological recognition has been the driving force behind the development of methods for elucidating the structure of their building blocks, monosaccharides. Hence, the three-dimensional structure and relative stability of all plausible conformers of monosaccharides, as well as their interaction with biochemical environments, continue being an area of great research activity.¹ Additionally, monosaccharides are also of interest in the field of astrophysics, where the ongoing search in the interstellar medium (ISM) has been able to detect, based on the rotational spectra identification, the simplest C₂ sugar,² but has yet to detect C₃³ sugars. Given the deficiency of accurate spectroscopic information, the detection of more complex sugars in the ISM is hindered. To date, rotational investigations of monosaccharides have been done for C₃ sugars,⁴ C₅ sugars⁵⁻⁷ and C₆ sugars,^{8,9} whereas the rotational studies of C₄ sugars have been limited to anhydrosugars.¹⁰ Thus, the most relevant C₄ sugar, D-erythrose, still remains elusive to experimental methods.

D-erythrose (C₄H₈O₄, see Chart 1), may be present in linear or cyclic furanose forms. Aqueous solution NMR studies^{11,12} have shown that furanose forms (25% and 65% of α and β furanose forms, respectively) are in equilibrium with an appreciable amount (~12 %) of acyclic forms. The formation of such five-membered ring structures in D-erythrose is the result of a nucleophilic reaction between the C₄ hydroxyl group and the aldehyde group, that give rise to hemiacetals, containing an asymmetric carbon C₁. This leads to the occurrence of two stereochemical α and β anomeric species, according to the position of the anomeric OH group (see Haworth projections in Chart 1). For each of these

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†Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: Predicted molecular properties for the lowest energy furanose and linear forms of D-erythrose, measured transition frequencies, cartesian coordinates for the observed conformers from MP2/6-311++G(d,p) calculations and complete ref 19. See DOI: 10.1039/b000000x/

anomers, puckering of the ring results in two configurations: the envelope (E), in which one ring atom lies out of a plane containing the remaining four; and the twist (T), in which two adjacent atoms lie above and below the plane defined by the remaining three. Ten envelope and ten twist configurations are plausible and are interconvertible by rotation of single bonds, giving the appearance of out-of-plane atoms rotating around the ring (pseudorotation¹³). This adds complexity, since each of these furanose rings may give rise to many conformers due to the relative arrangement of the OH groups, which form intramolecular hydrogen bonding network leading to a very complex conformational problem. A recent theoretical work¹⁴ of D-erythrose has predicted the existence of a large number of open chain and furanose conformations. Nevertheless, the actual structure of erythrose is still an enigma since to date no experimental data to validate the predicted conformational behaviour has been reported.

Chart 1. Fisher projection of D-erythrose (Center). Haworth projections

of the α and β anomers and sketch of the open chain form.

The combination of laser ablation with broadband Fourier transform microwave techniques^{15,16} has proved to be a very efficient way of delineating conformational landscapes of monosaccharides in the gas phase.⁶⁻⁸ The lack of gas phase investigations for erythrose is most likely due to the fact that it is a syrup at room temperature and thus, the standard attempt to bring it into the gas phase using conventional heating methods proved unsuccessful, due to thermal decomposition. In the present work we used a laser ablation technique and chirped pulse Fourier transform microwave (CP-FTMW) spectroscopy¹⁶ for characterizing D-erythrose in the gas phase. In the experimental procedure, some drops of D-erythrose (syrup ~75% of purity) were mixed with finely powdered NaCl and a small amount of Fig. 1. Broadband CP-FTMW rotational spectrum of D-erythrose and NaCl in the

* Rotamer A • Rotamer B

6–14 GHz frequency region. Top inset: detail of the CP-FTMW spectrum showing the feature ascribed to several transitions for both detected rotamers as well as some decomposition lines (See text).

a commercial binder. The mixture was pressed into cylindrical rods which in turn, were placed in the laser ablation nozzle and vaporized using the third harmonic (355 nm) of a ps laser. The vaporized products were seeded in Ne at backing pressure of 15 bar, and expanded adiabatically into the vacuum chamber of the spectrometer where they were probed by CP-FTMW. A high power excitation pulse of 300W was used to polarize the molecules from 6 to 14 GHz. 80000 individual free induction decays were averaged in the time domain and Fourier transformed to obtain the broadband frequency domain spectrum shown in Figure 1. The rotational spectrum was found to be dominated by the strong $J = 1 \leftarrow 0$ rotational transitions of Na^{35}Cl and Na^{37}Cl isotopic species in the ground and excited vibrational states at 13 GHz, as well as some common decomposition lines (ethylene glycol, acetic acid, formaldehyde and water complexes) found in previous studies of sugars.⁸ In an exhaustive inspection of the spectrum, we were able to observe additional weak lines, not present when pure NaCl samples were used, which were consequently attributed to D-erythrose conformers (See inset in Figure 1). It seems that NaCl molecules act as a carrier to bring erythrose molecules into the gas phase. After many attempts, μ_b and μ_c rotational transitions of a first rotamer (denoted as A), and μ_a and μ_c transitions belonging to a second species (designated as B), were assigned. The measured

transitions (see Tables S3-S4 in the Supporting Information) were fit¹⁷ using a rigid rotor Hamiltonian.¹⁸ The derived experimental rotational constants for both species are given in Table 1.

To ascertain which erythrose conformers are responsible for the observed spectrum, theoretical values of the rotational constants and electric dipole moment components of the most stable linear and furanose forms of D-erythrose are required. Thus, the lowest lying conformations¹⁴ in an energy window of 1000 cm^{-1} , were optimized using *ab initio* calculations at the MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level,¹⁹ providing the spectroscopic constants collected in Tables S1 and S2 of the Supplementary Information. The values of the experimental rotational constants of rotamer A were found to be consistent only with those predicted for the α envelopes forms, α -²E-cc or α -²E-c, of erythrose, presented also in Table 1. Because of the similar structures (which differ only in the clockwise or counterclockwise arrangements of OH groups) the values of the rotational constants alone do not allow a conclusive identification. The distinct arrangement of the OH groups in α -²E-cc or α -²E-c conformers has a huge effect on the values of the dipole moment components. Thus, the observation of μ_b -type and μ_c -type and the lack of μ_a -type transitions for rotamer A allows its unequivocal identification as conformer α -²E-cc (predicted as global minimum), taking in consideration the predicted values of the dipole moment components. In the same manner, the experimental rotational constants of rotamer B result compatible with those predicted for the two conformers β -¹T₂-cc or β -E₂-cc (collected also in Table 1 for comparison). As in the case of α -conformers, the observation of μ_a -type and μ_c -type rotational transitions for rotamer B is only consistent with the presence of β -¹T₂-cc conformer. Signals of the acyclic forms of erythrose could not be detected in the rotational spectrum. Indeed, linear form conformers have been predicted to lie 1800 cm^{-1} above the global minimum. Relative intensity measurements of rotational transitions indicate that D-erythrose exists in gas phase as a mixture of approximately equal amounts of α and of β furanose forms. This is in clear disagreement with the computed energies for both conformers; the α -²E-cc being predicted ca. 800 cm^{-1} more stable than β -¹T₂-cc. Consequently, it is reasonable to

Table 1 Experimental spectroscopic parameters for the two observed conformers of erythrose compared with those predicted at MP2/6-311++G(d,p).

	Rotamer A	α - ² E-cc ^c	α - ² E-c	Rotamer B	β - ¹ T ₂ -cc	β - ⁴ E-c
A ^a	2586.9010(11) ^b	2609.2	2626.9	3109.2009(98)	3107.3	2958.7
B	2353.0907(14)	2346.7	2263.1	1856.1295(11)	1865.0	2102.8
C	1773.23221(65)	1788.8	1814.4	1616.55508(98)	1642.2	1470.9
μ_a		0.30	-2.16	Observed	2.23	-0.61
μ_b	Observed	-1.90	-0.52		-0.14	-2.33
μ_c	Observed	-1.33	-0.05	Observed	1.11	-0.15
σ	5.2			8.4		
N	8			7		

^a A, B, and C represent the rotational constants (in MHz), μ_a , μ_b and μ_c are the absolute values of electric dipole moment components (in D), σ is the rms deviation of the fit (in kHz), N is the number of measured transitions. ^b Standard error in parentheses in units of the last digit. ^c The notation used to label the conformers include the symbols α and β to denote the anomer type, E and T with lower and upper subscripts indicate the ring puckerings,²⁰ and the symbols “c” or “cc” to indicate the clockwise or counter-clockwise configuration of the adjacent OH bonds, respectively.

5 assume that the D-erythrose gas phase composition in our experiment reflects the unknown proportion in the commercial syrup if the interconversion between α and β anomers does not occur during the laser ablation process or in gas phase.²¹

The good matching between experimental rotational constants and those predicted from the equilibrium structure (relative errors less than 1.0%) allows the assumption that the actual structures of both conformers are those predicted by *ab initio* calculations, depicted in Figure 2 (Cartesian coordinates for the *ab initio* predicted geometries are given in Table S5 of the Supporting Information). Cooperative hydrogen bonding is noticeably in the two observed conformers. Conformer α -²E-cc (Figure 2) presents the three hydroxyl groups on the same side of the furanose ring, oriented in such way as to allow the formation of a cyclic cooperative intramolecular hydrogen bond network, $\text{OH}_1 \cdots \text{OH}_3 \cdots \text{OH}_2 \cdots \text{OH}_1$ with a counter clockwise arrangement of the OH groups. Such arrangement of functional groups, specially the cyclic network, explains the stability associated to this conformer compared with the rest of the α -conformations that show, at most, three intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Meanwhile, for conformer β -¹T₂-cc (Figure 2), only two hydroxyl groups meet on the same side of the furanose ring. For this reason, at most two cooperative intramolecular hydrogen bonds can be established for this structure. Hence, $\text{OH}_3 \cdots \text{OH}_2 \cdots \text{O}_{\text{ring}}$ and $\text{OH}_1 \cdots \text{O}_{\text{ring}}$ hydrogen bond motifs together with the axial position of the hydroxyl group OH_1 (anomeric effect), are the main stabilizing factors within the β -¹T₂-cc conformer.

Fig. 2 The three dimensional structures of the two observed conformers of D-erythrose showing the intramolecular hydrogen bond networks. The distances are also indicated, in Å.

In summary, the present study provides the first reliable experimental information on the anomeric species of the D-erythrose and their dominant conformers in the gas phase. Two furanoside conformers, one α and one β , have been conclusively identified by the quantitative match between the experimental and calculated *ab initio* spectroscopic constants. An innovative experimental approach, using laser ablation of solid NaCl, has been used to bring syrup D-erythrose into the gas phase for a rotational

study. It can constitute a pioneering experimental method of obtaining the rotational spectra of liquids, which decompose before a suitable vapour pressure is achieved by traditional heating methods.

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References

- 1 J. P. Schermann, *Spectroscopy and Modeling of Biomolecular Building Blocks*; Elsevier, 2008.
- 2 (a) J. M. Hollis, F. J. Lovas, P. R. Jewell, *Astrophys. J.* 2000, **540**, L107; (b) J. M. Hollis, S. N. Vogel, L. E. Snyder, P. R. Jewell, F. J. Lovas, *Astrophys. J.* 2001, **554**, L81; (c) J. M. Hollis, P. R. Jewell, F. J. Lovas, P. Remijan, *Astrophys. J.* 2004, **613**, L45; (d) D. T. Halfen, A. J. Apponi, N. Woolf, R. Polt, L. M. Ziurys, *Astrophys. J.* 2006, **639**, 237; (e) M. T. Beltrán, C. Codella, S. Viti, R. Neri, R. Cesaroni, *Astrophys. J.* 2009, **690**, L93-L96; (f) J. K. Jørgensen, C. Favre, S. E. Bisschop, T. L. Bourke, E. F. van Dishoeck, M. Schmalzl, *Astrophys. J. Lett.* 2012, **757**, L4.
- 3 (a) J. M. Hollis, P. R. Jewell, F. J. Lovas, A. Remijan, H. Møllendal, *Astrophys. J.* 2004, **610**, L21; (b) A. J. Apponi, D. T. Halfen, L. M. Ziurys, J. M. Hollis, A. J. Remijan, F. J. Lovas, *Astrophys. J.* 2006, **643**, L29-L32.
- 4 F. J. Lovas, R. D. Suenram, D. F. Plusquellic, H. Møllendal, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 2003, **222**, 263.
- 5 E. J. Cocinero, A. Lesarri, P. Écija, F. J. Basterretxea, J.-U. Grabow, J. A. Fernández, F. Castaño, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2012, **51**, 3119-3124.
- 6 I. Peña, S. Mata, A. Martín, C. Cabezas, A. M. Daly, J. L. Alonso, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 2013, DOI: 10.1039/C3CP52345D.
- 7 I. Peña, E. J. Cocinero, C. Cabezas, A. Lesarri, S. Mata, P. Ecija, A. M. Daly, A. Cimas, C. Bermúdez, F. J. Basterretxea, S. Blanco, J. A. Fernández, J. C. López, F. Castaño, J. L. Alonso, 2013, DOI: 10.1002/anie.201305589.
- 8 C. Bermúdez, I. Peña, C. Cabezas, A. M. Daly, J. L. Alonso, *ChemPhysChem* 2013, **14**, 893-895.
- 9 E. J. Cocinero, A. Lesarri, P. Écija, B. G. Davis, A. Cimas, F. J. Basterretxea, J. A. Fernández, F. Castaño, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2013, **135**, 2845-2852.
- 10 B. M. Giuliano, S. Blanco, S. Melandri, W. Caminati, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 2008, **467**, 74-76, and references therein.
- 11 J. M. Risley, R. L. Van Etten, *Biochemistry* 1982, **21**, 6360-6365.
- 12 A. S. Serianni, J. Pierce, S. G. Huang, R. Barker, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1982, **104**, 4037-4044.
- 13 H. L. Strauss, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* 1983, **34**, 301.
- 14 L. M. Azofra, I. Alkorta, J. Elguero, P. L. A. Popelier, *Carbohydr. Res.* 2012, **358**, 96.
- 15 I. Peña, A. M. Daly, C. Cabezas, S. Mata, C. Bermúdez, A. Niño, J. C. López, J.-U. Grabow, J. L. Alonso, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 2013, **4**, 65-69.
- 16 S. Mata, I. Peña, C. Cabezas, J. C. López, J. L. Alonso, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 2012, **280**, 91-96.
- 17 H. M. Pickett, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1991, **148**, 371.
- 18 J. K. G. Watson, In *Vibrational Spectra and Structure*; J. R. Durig, Ed.; Elsevier: New York, 1977; Vol. 6, pp 1-78.

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- 19 M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Petersson, et al. *Gaussian 09*, Revision B.01. Wallingford CT, 2010.
- 5 20 P. Finch, *Carbohydrates: Structures, Syntheses and Dynamics*; Kluwer Academic Publishers: Netherlands 1999.
- 21 A. S. Serianni, D. M. Chipman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1987, **107**, 5297–5303.